

A Study on Growth and Performance of Automobile Industry in India : Its Comparison in Pre Covid and in Covid

ADITYA PRATAP SINGH AND RAJ BIHARI LAL SRIVASTAVA

Abstract : *The Automobile Industry is recognised as a core sector for any economy. Automobile industry in India contributes to 49% of India's manufacturing GDP. The Indian Automobile industry after surpassing Germany in terms of sales in 2020 became the 5th largest in the world. This study is based on secondary data which is collected from all the relevant sources. This study compares automobile production, Sales (Domestic, Exports) between FY 2015-19 (Pre Covid) to FY 2019-22 (In Covid) through the appropriate statistical tools like CAGR, AAGR and Correlation Coefficient. This study found that Automobile production, Sales was continuously increasing in pre covid but due to covid-19 pandemic this was drastically affected. However, in FY 2021-22, again it has shown some positive response in production and exports. This study also found that there is a positive high degree of correlation between FDI inflows in the Automobile industry and in Automobile production.*

Keywords : Automobile Industry, Coronavirus, Covid-19 Pandemic, Domestic Sales, Exports, FDI.

1. Introduction :

India is one of the fastest growing economies in the world. India in 2022 became the world's 5th largest economy in terms of nominal GDP and third largest in terms of GDP Purchasing Power Parity (PPP). Automobile industry plays a key role in the growth of the Indian economy. Nirmala Sitharaman, Finance Minister of India asserted that India will become 3rd largest in the world in the next 10-15 years (livemint, 2022). She has asserted this when India has surpassed the UK economy to become the 5th largest economy in the world. Narendra Modi, Prime Minister of India, said that India will become a 5 trillion-dollar economy by 2025-2026. And this is all possible due to the automobile industry. According

Aditya Pratap Singh, Research Scholar, Department of Commerce and Business Administration, University of Allahabad (U.P.)

Raj Bihari Lal Srivastava, Associate Professor, Department of Commerce and Business Administration, University of Allahabad (U.P.)

to cogoport.com the auto industry contributes to 49% in India's manufacturing GDP. India is the world's largest manufacturer of tractors. Similarly, India is a 2nd largest bus maker and 3rd largest in the manufacture of heavy trucks. According to fdi.finance, India is the largest two and three-wheeler vehicle manufacturer in the world. (fdi.finance, n.d.)

Automobile sector in India is divided into 4 different segments such as

1. Commercial Vehicles
2. Passenger Vehicles
3. Two Wheelers
4. Three Wheelers

As all other sectors depend on the automobile sector for their growth. The Government of India including all state governments invests huge amounts of money, changing policies for the growth of the automobile sector E.g., New electric vehicles.

2. Literature Review :

Melwani and Sitlani (2017) used time series analysis to analyse the export performance to forecast automobile trends. It was observed from their study that export in all the automobile segments has increased. Chattopadhyay and Mukherjee (2019) in his study, with the help of automobile production, automobile exports, domestic sales, FDI in automobile industry concluded that the Indian automobile sector is playing a key role for growth of an Indian economy. Chawla and Singh (2019) conducted a study to analyse the segment wise growth of the automobile industry. Throughout their research, they have used data from FY 2008-09 to FY 2018-19. This study concluded that automobile industry growth has declined due to decline in growth of passenger vehicles. Manickavasagam and Radhika (2019) examined the growth and performance of the Indian automobile industry. Throughout their study 5 Year's data have been collected from FY 2012-13 to 2017-18 to find out automobile production, domestic sales, and export statistics of different manufacturing companies and to find out the percentage of their contribution in the automobile industry. It was observed by their study that the Indian automobile industry is expected to reach Rs. 16.16 - 18.18 trillion by 2026. Chandrasekar and Palanivelu (2018) analysed trends and growth of the Indian automobile industry. It was observed by their study that the export growth rate of all types of vehicles was more than

the production growth rate of those vehicles. Rani and Ghosh (2020) conducted a study on Foreign Direct Investment in India. Their study analysed the FDI inflows in India and their contribution to different sectors. It was observed by the study that FDI inflows in India are rising and Mauritius being the top investing nation for India. Miglani (2019) conducted a study on growth of the Indian automobile industry. This study analyses the government roles and policies for the expansion of automobiles and its components. It is observed from the studies that government policies are helping in the expansion of the automobile industry. Vandana Singh (2017) conducted a study to analyse the Automobile industry as a multiplier effect for the growth of the economy. It was observed by the study that India automobile industries resulted in a strong multiplier effect for the growth of an Indian economy.

Several studies had already been done related to Indian automobile industry, their production, their sales either domestic or export but they all lack comparison of Indian automobile production, domestic sale, automobile exports in India before covid-19 pandemic and in covid-19 pandemic.

3 . Objectives of the Study :

1. To Compare automobile production in India, before covid 19 pandemic and In Covid 19 pandemic.
2. To Compare automobile sales (Domestic sales and exports) in India, before covid 19 pandemic and in covid 19 pandemic.
3. To study FDI inflows in the automobile industry in India and its correlation with total automobile production output before covid 19 pandemic.

4. Hypothesis for the Study :

H0 : There is no significant relation between FDI inflows in the Indian automobile industry and total automobile production output.

H1: There is a significant relation between FDI inflows in the Indian automobile industry and total automobile production output.

5. Research Methodology :

5.1. Sources of Data :

Throughout this study, secondary data has been collected from various annual reports, research articles and websites. The required data for this study has been

collected from the Department of Industrial Policy and Promotion (DIPP), Society of Indian Automobile Manufacturer (SIAM), India Brand Equity Foundation (IBEF).

5.2. Period of the Study :

For Comparison of Automobile production and Automobile Sales (domestic sales as well as export) in India, a period of 7 Financial years has been taken. In which FY 2015-16 to 2018-19 for pre covid and FY 2019-20 to 2021-22 for in Covid has been taken.

To study the correlation between the FDI inflows in the automobile industry in India and total production, a period of 9 financial years has been taken from the FY 2010-11 to 2018-19

5.3. Statistical Tools:

Throughout the Research study, Financial year data is analysed with the help of Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR), Average Annual Growth Rate (AAGR) and Correlation coefficient. For Comparison between pre covid and in Covid, tables are used in the study.

Calculation of Annual Growth Rate = [(New Investment Value - Old Investment Value) / Old Investment value * 100]

Calculation of AAGR = (Sum of all Annual Growth Rate / Numbers of Years).

Calculation of CAGR = [(Final Investment Value / Initial Investment Value)^{1 / Number of Years} -1]

6. Results and Findings :

6.1 Comparison of Indian Automobile Production : Before covid and In Covid

Indian automobile production Since LPG is increasing continuously but this could not continue due to covid-19 pandemic. The Automobile Sector is a key Sector for any economy and all other industries /sectors depend on this only for their growth. According to SIAM , India's automobile production in Financial Year (FY) 2010-11 is 1789 2409, In Financial Year (FY) 2015-16 is 24016068 which has increased to 30909 486 but, Due to covid-19 pandemic this has decreased to 22929169 in Financial Year 2021-2022. Table-1 shows the automobile production in commercial and passenger vehicles, two and three wheelers and its grand total. This all has been accompanied with their Annual growth rate over their previous year. Some key findings of above table are :

Table-1 : Indian Automobile Production in Terms of Numbers, Annual Growth Rate

Year	Annual				Annual				
	Commercial Vehicles	Growth Rate (%)	Passenger Vehicles	Growth Rate (%)	Two Wheelers	Annual Growth Rate (%)	Three Wheelers	Annual Growth Rate (%)	Grand Total
2015-16	786692		3465045		18830227		934104		24016068
2016-17	810253	2.99	3801670	9.71	19933739	5.86	783721	-16.10	25329383
2017-18	8,95,448	10.51	4020267	5.75	23154838	16.16	1022181	30.43	29092734
2018-19	11,12,405	24.23	4028471	0.20	24499777	5.81	1268833	24.13	30909486
AAGR	12.58 %		5.22 %		9.28 %		12.82 %		8.86 %
CAGR	12.24%		5.15%		9.17%		10.75%		8.78%
NOW, IN COVID 19 PANDEMIC									
2019-20	756725	-31.97	3424564	-14.99	21032927	-14.15	1132982	-10.71	26347198
2020-21	624939	-17.42	3062280	-10.58	18349941	-12.76	614613	-45.75	22651773
2021-22	805527	28.90	3650698	19.22	17714856	-3.46	758088	23.34	22929169
AAGR	-6.83 %		-2.12%		-10.12%		-11.04%		-9.19%
CAGR	3.17%		3.25%		-8.23%		-18.20%		-6.71%

Source : Society of Indian Automobile Manufacturers (SIAM)

- Average Annual Growth Rate (AAGR) of Automobile production is 8.86% in the Financial Year 2015-19 (Pre Covid) but this is decreased to -9.19% (Negative growth rate) in Financial Year 2019-22 (In Covid).
- Compound Annual Growth Rate of automobile production is 8.78% over the Financial Year 2015-19 (Pre Covid) but this decreased to -6.71% (Negative growth rate) over the Financial Year 2019-22 (In covid).
- Commercial vehicle segment with 12.24% CAGR is the fastest growing segment before Covid-19 pandemic . But in Covid-19 pandemic, Passenger vehicle segment with 3.25% CAGR is the fastest growing segment.
- Three-Wheeler segment with 10.75% CAGR is the second fastest growing segment before Covid 19 pandemic but this segment was drastically affected resulting in a Negative CAGR growth rate of -18.20%

6.2. Comparison of Indian Automobile Exports : Before Covid and In Covid

Export of any country decides the health of an economy. Export in economy shows the financial position of an economy such as Balance of Payment position. Export in any country plays a very important role to earn Foreign Exchanges.

Above table compare the in India Automobile export in terms of numbers, Annual growth rate AAGR, CAGR in pre Covid period from Financial Year 2015-16 to 2018-19 and In Covid period from the Financial Year 2019-20 to 2021-22. Some key findings of above comparison as follow :

- Average Annual Growth Rate (AAGR) being 8.70% over the Financial Year 2015-19 in Pre Covid-19 pandemic and 8.51% in Financial Year 2019-22 (In Covid).
- Average Annual Growth Rate (AAGR) of three-wheeler is 18.79% is the largest growth rate in pre Covid followed by two-wheeler with 10.37%.
- Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) being 8.27% over the financial year 2015-19 (Before Covid pandemic) and it is 8.78% in the Financial Year 2019-22 (In Covid).
- Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of Three-wheeler is the fastest growing segment in pre Covid with 11.97% whereas Commercial vehicles is the fastest growing segment with 23.64%.

Table-2 : Indian Automobile Export in Terms of Numbers, Annual Growth Rate

Year	Annual		Annual		Annual		Annual		Annual	
	Commercial Vehicles	Growth Rate(%)	Passenger Vehicles	Growth Rate(%)	Two Wheelers	Growth Rate(%)	Three Wheelers	Growth Rate(%)	Grand Total	Growth Rate(%)
2015-16	103124		653053		2482876		404441		3643494	
2016-17	108271	4.99	758727	16.18	2340277	-5.74	271894	-32.77	3479169	-4.51
2017-18	96865	-10.53	748366	-1.37	2815003	20.29	381002	40.13	4041236	16.16
2018-19	99933	3.17	676192	-9.64	3280841	16.55	567683	49.00	4624649	14.44
AAGR	-0.79 %		1.72%		10.37%		18.79%			8.70%
CAGR	-1.04%		1.17%		9.73%		11.97%			8.27%
NOW , IN COVID 19 PANDEMIC										
2019-20	60379	-39.58	662118	-2.08	3519405	7.27	501651	-11.63	4743553	2.57
2020-21	50334	-16.64	404397	-38.92	3282786	-6.72	393001	-21.66	4130518	-12.92
2021-22	92297	83.37	577875	42.90	4443018	35.34	499730	27.16	5612920	35.89
AAGR	9.05%		0.63%		11.96%		-2.04%			8.51%
CAGR	23.64%		-6.58%		12.36%		-0.19%			8.78%

Source : Society of Indian Automobile Manufacturers (SIAM)

- Commercial vehicles were showing Negative CAGR before Covid 19 pandemic with - 1.04% but in Covid 19 pandemic, this segment with growth rate of 23.64% (Positive Growth Rate) was fastest and highest growth among all other Segments.

6.3. Comparison of Indian Automobile Domestic Sales : Before Covid and In Covid

Table-3 above depicts automobile domestic sales of Commercial vehicles, Passenger vehicles, Two and Three-wheeler, Grand total in terms of numbers annual growth rate in Pre Covid and In Covid. Some key findings of above comparisons is as follow :

- Average Annual Growth Rate (AAGR) was 8.74% in the financial year 2015-19 (Before Covid 19 pandemic) whereas AAGR for financial 2019-22 showed a negative growth rate of -12.49% (In Covid).
- Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) was 8.67% in the financial year 2015-19 (Before Covid 19 pandemic) whereas the CAGR for financial 2019-22 showed a negative growth rate of -9.84% (In Covid) .
- Commercial vehicles are the fastest growing segment in the financial year 2015-19 followed by Three wheelers in both the terms AAGR and CAGR. AAGR with 13.9 % and CAGR with 13.68%.
- Three wheelers showed the highest Negative growth rate both in terms of AAGR and CAGR in the financial year 2019-22 (In Covid). AAGR with negative growth rate of -18.58% and CAGR with negative growth rate of -35.99%.

6.4. Total Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) Inflows in India

According to the PIB, press release, India with US dollar 83.57 billion in FY 2021-22 recorded the highest ever annual Foreign Direct Investment inflows . India inflows in FY 2021-22 is 20 times more than Financial year 2003-04 when FDI inflow was only 4.3 billion only. According to the report, FDI equity inflow in FY 2021-22 rose by 76% in the manufacturing sector. According to the report, FDI inflows from March 2020 to March 2022 Rose by 23% as compared to Feb 2018 to Feb 2020. Karnataka being the top receipt state in India with 38% FDI followed by Maharashtra with 26% and Delhi with 14%.

Table-3 : Indian Automobile Domestic Sales in Terms of Numbers, Annual Growth Rate

Year	Annual			Annual			Annual			Annual		
	Commercial Vehicles	Growth Rate(%)	Passenger Vehicles	Growth Rate(%)	Two Wheelers	Growth Rate(%)	Three Wheelers	Growth Rate(%)	Grand Total	Growth Rate(%)	Annual Growth Rate(%)	
2015-												
16	685704		2789208		16455851		538208		20468971			
2016-												
17	714082	4.14	3047582	9.26	17589738	6.89	511879	-4.89	21863281	6.81		
2017-												
18	856916	20.00	3288581	7.91	20200117	14.84	635698	24.19	24981312	14.26		
2018-												
19	1007311	17.55	3377389	2.70	21179847	4.85	701005	10.27	26265552	5.14		
AAGR		13.9%		6.62%		8.86%		9.86%		8.74%		
CAGR		13.68%		6.59%		8.78%		9.21%		8.67%		
NOW , IN COVID 19 PANDEMIC												
2019-												
20	717593	-28.76	2773519	-17.88	17416432	-17.77	637065	-9.12	21544609	-17.97		
2020-												
21	568559	-20.77	2711457	-2.24	15120783	-13.18	219446	-65.55	18620245	-13.57		
2021-												
22	716566	26.03	3069499	13.20	13466412	-10.94	260995	18.93	17513472	-5.94		
AAGR		-7.83%		-2.30%		-13.96%		-18.58%		-12.49%		
CAGR		-0.07%		5.20%		-12.07%		-35.99%		-9.84%		

Source : Society of Indian Automobile Manufacturers (SIAM)

Table-4 : FDI Inflows in Terms of - US\$ in Millions and Annual Growth Rate

FINACIAL YEAR (1st April - 31st March)	PERCENTAGE GROWTH				PERCENTAGE GROWTH				PERCENTAGE GROWTH			
	EQUITY INFLOWS (A)	EQUITY CAPITAL (B)	PREVIOUS YEAR	OVER PREVIOUS YEAR	REINVESTED EARNINGS	PREVIOUS YEAR	OVER PREVIOUS YEAR	OTHER CAPITAL	PREVIOUS YEAR	OVER PREVIOUS YEAR	TOTAL FDI INFLOWS	OVER PREVIOUS YEAR
2010-11	21376	874			11939			658			34847	
2011-12	34833	1022	62.95	16.93	8206		-31.27	2495		279.18	46556	33.60
2012-13	21825	1059	-37.34	3.62	9880		20.40	1534		-38.52	34298	-26.33
2013-14	24299	975	11.34	-7.93	8978		-9.13	1794		16.95	36046	5.10
2014-15	30933	978	27.30	0.31	9988		11.25	3249		81.10	45148	25.25
2015-16	40001	1111	29.31	13.60	10413		4.26	4034		24.16	55559	23.06
2016-17	43478	1223	8.69	10.08	12343		18.53	3176		-21.27	60220	8.39
2017-18	44857	664	3.17	-45.71	12542		1.61	2911		-8.34	60974	1.25
2018-19	44366	689	-1.09	3.77	13672		9.01	3274		12.47	62001	1.68
NOW , IN COVID 19 PANDEMIC												
2019-20	49977	1757	12.65	155.01	14175		3.68	8482		159.07	74391	19.98
2020-21	59636	1787	19.33	1.71	16216		14.40	4082		-51.87	81721	9.85
CAGR	10.80%	7.41%			3.11%			20.02%			8.90%	

Source : (Kumar, 2021) <https://globalpresshub.com/index.php/ABAAR/article/view/1312/1085>

Note :

(A) RBI Automatic/FIPB Route / Acquisition Route

(B) Equity capital of the unincorporated bodies

Above table shows total FDI inflows in India with annual growth rate and Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) over the Financial Year 2010-11 to 2020-21.

6.5. FDI Inflows in Automobile Sector from Total FDI inflows in India :

Table-5 : Comparison of FDI Inflows in Automobile Sector from Total FDI Inflows – in Terms of Crores and Annual Growth Rate

Financial Year	Total FDI Inflows in India (Cr)	% Growth over Previous year	Total FDI Inflows in automobile Industry (Cr)	% Growth over the previous year	Share of FDI inflow in Automobile industry to total FDI inflows
2010-11	97320		5864		6.03
2011-12	165146	69.69	4347	-25.87	2.63
2012-13	121907	-26.18	8384	92.87	6.88
2013-14	147518	21.01	9027	7.67	6.12
2014-15	181682	23.16	16760	85.67	9.22
2015-16	262322	44.39	16437	-1.93	6.27
2016-17	291696	11.20	10824	-34.15	3.71
2017-18	288889	-0.96	13461	24.36	4.66
2018-19	309867	7.26	18309	36.02	5.91
	1866347		103413		
Total CAGR		15.58%		15.29%	

Source : Society of Indian Automobile Manufacturers (SIAM)

Above table represents FDI inflows in the automobile Industry in Crores for the Financial Year 2010-11 to 2018-19, a period of 9 Financial Years and percentage growth of its previous year . Above table also depicts the share of FDI inflows in the automobile industry to total FDI inflows in India. Some key findings of above table is as follows :

- Total FDI inflows in the automobile industry is Rs.103413 crores from Financial year 2010-11 to 2018-19.

- In 9 Financial years of study , FDI growth rate over previous years in the automobile industry was maximum in 2012-13 with 92.87% followed by 85.67% in 2014-15, followed by 36.02% in FY 2018-19.
- Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) was 15.29% in FDI inflows in the automobile Industry from the Financial year 2010-11 to 2018-19.

6.6. Correlation Analysis between FDI inflows in Automobile Industry and Total Automobile Production Output.

Table-6 : Correlation Coefficient to find Relation between FDI Inflows in Automobile Industry and Total Automobile Production Output

Financial Year	FDI inflows in Automobile industry in Crores (X)	Total No. of Vehicles Production in Crores (Y)
2010-11	5864	1789
2011-12	4347	2038
2012-13	8384	2064
2013-14	9027	2150
2014-15	16760	2335
2015-16	16437	2401
2016-17	10824	2532
2017-18	13461	2909
2018-19	18309	3091
Correlation Coefficient	0.764670149	

Table-6 above, shows the Correlation coefficient between Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) inflows in the automobile industry and total number of automobile production. In the above table (X) is taken for FDI inflows in the automobile industry and (Y) is taken as the total number of Automobile production output . Above figures are in Crores. For Correlation Coefficient r is taken. After applying Correlation coefficient for X and Y, the correlation Coefficient r is 0.7646. This shows that there is a positive high degree of Correlation Coefficient between FDI inflow in the automobile industry and the total number of automobile production output.

Above calculation is shown in the Appendix. Above result resulted in **Rejection of Null Hypothesis and acceptance of Alternate Hypothesis.**

Conclusion:

- The present study analysed Automobile production (Commercial vehicles, passenger vehicles, two wheelers and three wheelers) in terms of numbers, Annual Growth Rate, AAGR and CAGR in Pre Covid and In Covid. This is observed from the table-1 that the AAGR of automobile production is positive AAGR of 8.86 % in pre covid. Whereas it is negative AAGR of -9.19% in covid-19 pandemic. Similarly, CAGR for same period is 8.79% before Covid 19 pandemic and its negative CAGR with -6.71 % in covid-19 pandemic.
- The present study analysed Automobile Exports (Commercial vehicles, passenger vehicles, two wheelers and three wheelers) in terms of numbers, Annual Growth Rate, AAGR and CAGR in Pre Covid and In Covid. This is observed from table-2 that the AAGR of automobile production is positive AAGR with 8.70% for pre covid period. Whereas it is 8.51% in covid-19 pandemic. But, the CAGR for pre covid is only 8.27% which is less than 8.78% of Covid 19 pandemic period and this is due to excessive export in 2021-22.
- The present study analysed Automobile domestic sales (Commercial vehicles, passenger vehicles, two wheelers and three wheelers) in terms of numbers, Annual Growth Rate, AAGR and CAGR in Pre Covid and In Covid. This is observed from table-3 that the AAGR of automobile production is positive AAGR of 8.74% in pre covid. But due to Covid 19 pandemic , people lost their jobs which has affected their earning as well as their savings and due to this AAGR for in Covid period is negative growth

rate of -12.49% . Similarly, CAGR is 8.67% for pre covid pandemic and it is negative CAGR growth rate in covid-19 pandemic with -9.84%.

- The present study also analyses the FDI inflows from all sectors and their annual growth rate over previous years. This is shown in table-4 above. Similarly, table-5 analyses FDI inflows in the automobile industry and percent growth over previous year.
- The present study also analyses the FDI inflow in automobile industry and total number of Automobile production output through Correlation coefficient. It was observed from the table 6 calculation that both have a high degree of positive correlation of 0.7646.

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APPENDIX :**Table-6 : Calculation****CORRELATION ANALYSIS –**

Financial Year	FDI inflows in Automobile industry in Crores (X)	Total No. of Vehicles Production in Crores (Y)	XY	X²	Y²
2010-11	5864	1789	10490696	34386496	3200521
2011-12	4347	2038	8859186	18896409	4153444
2012-13	8384	2064	17304576	70291456	4260096
2013-14	9027	2150	19408050	81486729	4622500
2014-15	16760	2335	39134600	280897600	5452225
2015-16	16437	2401	39465237	270174969	5764801
2016-17	10824	2532	27406368	117158976	6411024
2017-18	13461	2909	39158049	181198521	8462281
2018-19	18309	3091	56593119	335219481	9554281
Total	103413	21309	257819881	1389710637	51881173

$$\bar{X} = 103413 / 9 = 11490.33$$

$$\bar{Y} = 21309 / 9 = 2367.67$$

$$r = \frac{(n(\sum xy) - (\sum x)(\sum y))}{(\sqrt{[n\sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2][n\sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2]}}$$

$$r = 0.764670149$$